

ANALASING THE POSSIBLE CAUSES OF NEGATIVE ATTITUDES TOWARDS THE USE OF THE ANGOLAN ‘NATIONAL LANGUAGES’ IN LOBITO: A SOCIOLINGUISTICS CASE STUDY.

ANALISANDO AS POSSÍVEIS CAUSAS DAS ATITUDES NEGATIVAS EM RELAÇÃO À UTILIZAÇÃO DAS ‘LÍNGUAS NACIONAIS’ ANGOLANAS NO LOBITO: UM ESTUDO DE CASO DE SOCIOLINGUÍSTICA.

ANÁLISIS DE LAS POSIBLES CAUSAS DE LAS ACTITUDES NEGATIVAS HACIA EL USO DE LAS ‘LENGUAS NACIONALES’ ANGOLANAS EN LOBITO: UN ESTUDIO DE CASO SOCIOLINGÜÍSTICO.

ANALYSE DES CAUSES POSSIBLES DES ATTITUDES NÉGATIVES À L’ÉGARD DE L’UTILISATION DES ‘LANGUES NACIONALES’ ANGOLAISES À LOBITO: UNE ÉTUDE DE CAS SOCIOLINGUISTIQUE.

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the possible causes of negative attitudes towards use of the Angolan ‘national languages’ in Lobito. The study aims at looking at the implications of negative attitudes towards the use of national languages in terms of social, economic and political exclusions of people who cannot communicate in Portuguese language as the main medium of instructions and social mobility. To collect data, we used a semi-structured interview at Complexo Escolar BGN 2012 Evangélico da Canata- Lobito, where (2) two school administratives were selected and (9) nine teachers from different schools in Lobito. The participants were originally from different ethno-linguistic groups (Ovimbundu, Mbundu, Bakongo, etc). The findings show that linguistic heterogeneity creates social and cultural stigmatisation that lead to marginalisation and exclusion. The marginalizations and stigmatizations are associated to lack of prestige and the market value of ‘ national

languages.

Keywords: Language attitudes, Negative attitudes, causes, ‘national languages’ and Angola.

RESUMO

O presente estudo aborda as atitudes negativas em relação ao uso das línguas nacionais angolanas no Lobito. A investigação centra-se, fundamentalmente, nas implicações dessas atitudes negativas em termos de exclusão social, económica e política das comunidades com baixa fluência na Língua Portuguesa, entendida como língua de instrução e de mobilidade social.

Para a recolha de dados, recorreu-se à entrevista semiestruturada, realizada no Complexo Escolar BGN 2012 Evangélico da Canata, no Lobito. Participaram dois responsáveis administrativos e nove professores das disciplinas de Língua Portuguesa, Língua Inglesa e Umbundu. Foram seleccionados participantes pertencentes a diferentes grupos etnolinguísticos, nomeadamente Ovimbundu, Mbundu e Bakongo, entre outros.

Concluiu-se que a heterogeneidade linguística pode contribuir para fenómenos de marginalização e discriminação social e cultural. A marginalização, a discriminação e a exclusão social e cultural estão fortemente associadas à falta de prestígio e ao reduzido valor de mercado atribuídos às línguas nacionais.

Palavras Chaves: Atitudes linguísticas, Atitudes Negativas, Causas, línguas nacionais e Angola.

RESUMEN

O presente estudo faz uma abordagem sobre as atitudes negativas sobre o uso das línguas "nacionais Angolanas" no Lobito. El estudio se enfoca principalmente en las implicaciones de las actitudes negativas sobre el uso de las lenguas nacionales en términos de inclusión social, económica y política de las comunidades que tienen fluidez en comunicarse, en lengua portuguesa como lengua de instrucción y movilidad social. En términos metodológicos, é uma pesquisa de naturalza de caso estudo qualitativo y descriptivo, com vista a colher dados. Usou-se entrevista semi-estructurada no Complexo Escolar BGN 2012

Evangélico da Canata-Lobito, onde selecionamos dois (2) jefes administrativos, nove (9) profesores de linguas portuguesas, inglesas y umbundu. Os entrevistados são pertencentes a diferentes grupos etnolinguísticos (Ovimbundu, Mbundu, Bakongo, etc). Concluimos que la diversidad lingüística causa tensiones discursivas y culturales que resultan en jerarquía y marginación. El estigma y la marginación asociados a las “lenguas nacionales” y a sus falantes son consecuencias del prestigio y valor de Mercado atribuído a la lengua portuguesa.

Palabras-clave. Atitudes linguísticas, Atitudes Negativas, la causas, línguas nacionais e Angola.

RESUMÉ

Il s’agit d’un sujet d’abordage concernant les attitudes négatives concernant l’utilisation des langues «nationales angolaises» à Lobito. L’étude se concentre fondamentalement sur les implications des attitudes négatives concernant l'utilisation des langues nationales en termes d'inclusion sociale, économique et politique des communautés qui ont une maîtrise de la communication dans la langue portugaise comme langue d'enseignement et de mobilité sociale. En termes méthodologiques, c'est une tâche de nature de cas d'étude qualitative et descriptive, avec vue sur d'autres données. Nous avons été interviewés semi-structurés dans le Complexo Escolar BGN 2012 Evangélico da Canata-Lobito, où nous avons sélectionné deux (2) chefs administratifs, nouveaux (9) professeurs de langues portugaises, anglaises et umbundu. Les interviewés appartiennent à différents groupes ethnolinguistiques (Ovimbundu, Mbundu, Bakongo, etc.). Nous concluons que la diversité linguistique provoque des tensions discursives et culturelles qui entraînent une hiérarchie et une marginalisation. L’estigme et la marginalisation associées aux « langues nationales » et à leurs faiblesses sont la conséquence du prestige et de la valeur du marché attribué à la langue portugaise.

Mots-clés: Atitudes linguísticas, Atitudes négativas, cause, langue mationale et Angola.

INTRODUCTION

The classic definition of an attitude is that Ruth and Zipp, (2022) who view it as “a mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individuals’ response to all objects and situations which it is related”. It can also be defined as “a disposition to respond favorably or unfavorably to an object, person, institution, or event”. One would expect the speakers of ‘national language’ to be proud of their own languages, but quite often one encounters negative attitudes. One of the most common features of negative attitudes towards the national languages is that of elites who prefer education in the ex-colonial languages and these make those parents belonging to lower social groups also want the same education for their children. As Romaine (1994) claims, what influences certain way of speaking to be considered as more important, sometimes viewed as prestigious it is because the upper class or the elites speak this language. (p, 33).

This means that Portuguese is taken as the language of science, technology and economic transactions. Moreover, Holmes (2013) adds that:

People generally do not hold opinions about languages in a vacuum. They develop attitudes towards languages, which indicate their views about those who speak the language, and the contexts and functions with which they are associated. When people listen to accents or languages they have never heard before, their assessments are totally random... There is no universal consensus about which languages sound most beautiful and which most ugly, despite people’s beliefs that some languages are just inherently more beautiful than others. (p,431).

That is to say, language attitudes, whether negative or positive, are also associated with the people who use the it and the functions they play within the communities. The kind of attitude is greatly related to the beliefs that grows in a particular community. Sallabank (2013) says that negative attitudes are not necessarily revealed through direct questions, but are inferred or deducted from discourses and by observing behaviour and practices. Language attitudes are normally inferred from people’s interaction, behaviour and

communicative practices. (p, 130).

The marginalization of the “national languages” is associated with the low prestige and lack of status within a community where the Portuguese is the dominant language. This affects people in terms of having access to social services, such as education, economic and the effective participation and contribution in the community. A very important question that has to be asked is really to understand the nature of language attitudes. Coupland, Williams and Peter (2006) say that language attitudes covers what a person has acquired while becoming a member of a family, a member of certain community or society that shapes his or her behavior according to the norms and principles around. Therefore, we can perceive it as an outcoming that reflects a person long time process of socialization. However, attitudes to languages are likely to change depending on a person’s particular interest at a certain point of their life. (p,5). Manuel (2022) claims that in Angola, the fact that Portuguese is the only official language it operates symbolically and represents a contested space. Moreover, it is used as an instrument of national unity and a site for the construction of national identity. The relation between linguistic structure and discourse implies that power operates by producing homogeneity and stratifying languages and discourse. (p, 33).

Language attitudes are also reflexive of the policy that has been adopted in the country because it is the duty of the policy makers to conceive a language policy that benefits the mutual cohabitation of all the languages in certain region, mainly in a multilingual and multicultural society.

In this study, we are going to look at the possible causes of negative attitudes towards the use of national languages and their implications in Lobito. Although, the study has been carried out in Lobito, it is considered as the problem is of national interest. Negative language attitudes are synonymous with denying people’s rights to integrate fully in a society and creating social exclusion by perpetuating Portuguese language and those use it as the most intelligent and educated.

DOMAIN OF USE: WHO USES LOCAL LANGUAGES, WHEN, WHERE, HOW AND WHY?

Richards and Schmidt (2010) say that domain of language refers to code choice in bilingual or multilingual contexts in which two or more languages are used for different domains.

(p,182). Wilson and Holmes (2017) argue that there are social factors that influence the domain of language use, for example, the person that we are talking to, the social context that the interaction is taking place, the function and the topic of the discussion. (p, 21). Holmes (2008) adds that the domain of language use in a community helps to be aware of the norms of language use. Moreover, Coulmas (2005) states that domains that are normally identified include home, work, school, church, market, government and leisure. (p,138). Sallabank (2013) agrees that the status attributed to ‘national languages’ is hugely limited and these languages are endangered in terms of their by the wider community. (p, 96). Finally, Webb and Kembo- Sure (2010) reflect on the domains of use of the local or ‘national languages’, that ‘national languages’ have an extremely low status; those who speak these languages (‘national languages’) do not believe that they can be used in public or secondary) domains of life, as instruments of learning, economic activity, social mobility, or for any other serious public business. They often argue that their primary languages do not have the necessary vocabulary and speech styles, or sufficient status to be used spontaneously in public domains, and it therefore makes no sense to study them at school...they are only useful as instruments of interpersonal social interaction and cultural expression within the community (,p. 15).

That is to say, in terms of the domain of use, ‘national languages’ have a very limited use. Because of not speaking the portuguese language well, People tend to isolate themselves from the whole community. This brings forth an ideology that ‘national languages’ are not worth for education, technology and science. However, we can advocate that all languages are of equal value, because they can be used as instruments to express whatever their speakers intend to communicate and they are linguistically equipped with elements to have effective communication. Tchimboto (2024) claims that the domain of ‘national languages’ is also restricted to traditional social organization, such as traditional courts, weddings and religious cultural practices. (p,75).

Looking at Tchimboto’s assertions, it is clear that the use of ‘national languages’ is related to the traditional issues in the communities for religious and cultural practices. This means that even in the rural areas children speak ‘national languages’ at home, but have to turn to Portuguese at school. This practices influence hugely the children learning because they have to make an effort to speak in a language they cannot speak well.

LANGUAGE AS A RESOURCE, LANGUAGE AS PROBLEM, AND LANGUAGE AS RIGHT.

Alstad and Sopenan (2020) claims that one of the instruments for assessing ideologies in language policy is called language orientations. These orientations are termed as set of values for languages and multilingualism. These are also defined as “ideologies or orientations as a complex of dispositions...towards language and its role- related to language attitudes in that they constitute the framework in which attitudes are formed.” Furthermore, there are three orientations in policies such as, language as problem, language as right and language as resources.

The language-as-problem orientation stresses on monolingualism and the majority language in both society and education, and views language diversity as a social problem that should be solved; linguistic diversity and minority are not claimed as important and seen as useless. Language as right orientations emphasize minority languages and allow the speakers of these languages to use it and they can use it as a medium of instruction. Finally, language as resources orientations, in Kamwangamalu (2016) looks at linguistic diversity as a great resource and aims at the “development, preservation, and use of the languages in many domains especially in such critical domains as education and the media, and other wide means of communication”.

The three orientations above are the main frameworks in which language policy is conceived. However, the language-as-problem orientation that has been adopted in Angola marginalizes the ‘national languages’ and upholds the Portuguese as the sole official language used in government institutions.

NATIONAL LANGUAGE, OFFICIAL LANGUAGE AND REGIONAL LANGUAGE

According to Jimbi and Sicala (2022), in order to understand the concept of national languages, one has to consider it in both the strict sense and broader terms. In the strict sense, “national language” is referred to as the language that is seen as a source or sign of identity for a nation. For example, the Ovambo makes a precolonial nation whose language is Oshikwanyama. In the broader sense, a national language can be termed as any of the regional languages that is found that in a territory. For example, Umbundu and Kimbundu are widely regarded as national languages in Angola.

However, the nation-state building in multilingual postcolonial countries may lead to the removal of the minority languages mainly when the rulers view these languages, as a threat to the unity of the population's socio-political and economic objectives. Furthermore, most African countries, including Angola, are still under colonial language policy in which the Portuguese has been chosen as the only official language with the nationwide coverage.(p,62-63). The fact that many indigenous languages are designated as national languages in Angola, in real terms most people still feel embarrassed to use them comparing to the Portuguese language. This kind of marginalization excludes people from their basic rights to education, health care and cannot grow and progress in their own languages. Jimbi & Sicala, (2022) affirm that

Most often, the concept of national language is understood as including one or various languages that can stand as symbols or as a source of identity and cultural integration of the nation but that are not necessarily recognized as official languages. (Op.cit).

Philipson, (1992), Matthews (2007) and Richards and Schmidt (2010) define a national language as one that is spoken by the majority of the population and is, in general, a vernacular language of the population, that use it either officially or not, and which may or may not be used in the educational system. That is, the law on the constitution can also reinforce the concepts of national languages. (p,258-285-6).

Finally, Jimbi and Sicala (2022) explain that to define a "national language" in a multilingual country, like Angola has yet been a contentious issue because any specific language has been determined as a "national language". Unless the law names specific languages to be called "national languages". Thus, "national languages" are spoken regionally with limited geographical and population density. However, ideologically and for maintaining the national unity, national languages are "understood as including one or various languages that can stand as symbols or source of identity and cultural integration of the nation but that are not necessarily recognized as official languages. (p,63).

We could claim that the concept of national languages is ideologically associated, in postcolonial Angola to maintain the nation united; because these languages are autonomous and regionally spoken by specific ethno-linguistic groups and centered within a particular geographical space. For example, the Ovimbundu ethno-linguistic group corresponds a region whose language spoken is Umbundu and the Mbundu groups speak Kimbundu which

makes specific regions. Furthermore, in postcolonial Angola, a contrast could be made with the Portuguese with almost the nationwide coverage and in comparison with the ‘national languages’ which many people feel ashamed to use them.

THE LEGACY OF COLONIALISM IN ANGOLAN LANGUAGE POLICY

According to Manuel and Johnson (2018), in the 1960s, Africa registered a great demand of nationalistic movements for decolonization and political independence. There were many problems to solve, economic, political, self-determination, and obviously a very important question that was raised about which languages would be used for nation-building and social development, and this question has been known as Africa’s *language question*. Many policies have been adopted including the Cultural Charter for Africa, which aimed at “promoting the introduction of African languages at all levels of education”. Manuel and Johnson (2018) formulate that despite these initiatives and policies promoting African languages, many African languages (and their speakers) are still marginalized in education contexts. Sub-Saharan Africa is characterized by complex multilingualism and this diversity is often used to justify adopting ex- colonial languages (English, French, and Portuguese) as *língua Franca*, official languages, and or the preferred medium of instruction in countries like Mozambique, Liberia, and Angola where language in education policy is but one part of a larger economic structure, which continues the legacy of colonialism. (p, 2).

Jimbi and Sicala (2022) reinforces that colonial economic relationships are perpetuated through labour and market arrangements that privilege global economic control for ex-colonizers. The famous decree ‘77’ issued on 9 December 1921 under José Mendes Ribeiro Norton de Matos, who was Governor General of the then Portuguese province of Angola banned the use of the indígenas’s languages. Norton de Matos’decree has influenced hugely the current practices of language policy in Angola and the status that national languages attributed. (p. 67).

The Portuguese language continues to be the only official language in Angola where there are other other local languages, it reflects a kind of policy that has been adopted from the colonial power. This means that the rulers have to fight for linguistic independence. Linguistic Independence implies not to be stuck on the colonial language policy.

MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTIONS AS AN INHERITANCE SITUATION

According to Manuel and Johnson (2018) medium of instruction policies in Africa in general and in Angola in particular, have been following the colonial legacy of European language dominance, “marginalization of national languages, and unequal educational opportunities”. Moreover, Portuguese is the mother tongue for most Angolans and those who do not speak it are said to find huge difficulties to overcome the school subjects and interact with teachers and classmates (p, 2). Webb & Kembo- Sure (2010), add that for most African countries, the medium of instruction is strictly associated with the standard language, the standard language is connected to prestige, and elite groups, promoting unified norms and regional differences, and when it is institutionalized, it can be used in the mass media, as medium of instructions. (p,65).

Furthermore, McKay and Hornberger (1996) reinforce that the selection of a particular language or linguistic variant either as object or medium of instruction is never isolated but a sign of power relationships and social dominance caused by language or language varieties in any society. (p,26). However, Kamwangamalu (2016) states that studies demonstrate that children have better performance at school when they are taught through the medium of instruction of the regional variety or related indigenous language rather than a foreign medium of instruction. There exists a relationship between the medium of instruction and the performance of children at school and the academic development. (p,111).

Fernando, Paxe and Ngulube, (2020) adds that if the schooling is done in a language that both teachers and the learners cannot master well, it becomes a limitation factor and barrier between what the learner gets from school and he or she lives in a daily life, causing a clash between what is learned and the cultural reality. (p, 196). Finally, Zsiga et al. (2014) add that:

The Angolan government] is looking beyond issues of children children’s access to schooling, to focus on educational quality. In this context, literacy learning becomes central, and with it, unresolved issues of language choice for schooling in multilingual situations... the issue on how to build knowledge and skills out of children already know- especially their language resources. It is not enough to make sure that children are in school. Educators and parents also need to make sure that schools are providing students the education they need to succeed while there will be

support for bilingual education that includes African languages, changing the medium of instruction policies will be an uphill battle, especially when language ideologies supporting the hegemonic status of the former colonial language, Portuguese, [French] and the growing influence of English, remain so entrenched. (p, 7).

We have to argue that there is still a great challenge in most African countries in general, and in Angola in particular, concerning to the choice of language as medium of instruction in schools, most importantly because most African countries are multilingual and they cohabit with the ex-colonial languages. The choice of medium of instruction in schools is directly associated with the prestige, power and elitism. That is why, the language of instruction in Lobito as in the whole country is still Portuguese, because the legacy of Portuguese as a dominant language remains. This ideology keeps the view that Portuguese language is related to better literacy, economy and technology. Moreover, the use of Portuguese as the medium of instructions in schools also has a discriminatory view and social exclusion, because there are many families whose the main medium for communication are ‘national languages’.

COLONIAL IDEOLOGIES REDUX: THE DOMINANCE OF PORTUGUESE

Manuel and Johnson (2018), Comment that ‘Portuguese is the language that is spoken in Angola and people who want to succeed should master it’. Even those who are in favour of bilingual education recognize the Portuguese language as has a very important role in modern Angolan society. ‘The national languages’, parallel with the Portuguese, however, they admit the dominance of Portuguese as the language of education and socioeconomic opportunity. (p,11).

Supporting this belief Manuel and Johnson, (2018) claim is the perspective that African languages are not appropriate for educational contexts because they are less developed, ‘backward’, or because there is lack of educational resources to support mother tongue education, (p.10). In addition, Manuel and Johnson (2018), add that, there still sceptism about the official teaching of national languages [African languages]. One of the doubts is: what will be technical and scientific significance of learning national languages? At

the outset, we believe that in primary school, which is the most important stage, knowledge of Portuguese grammar must be consolidated as a basis for learning any other language and other scientific content matters. (p.11) For us the vocabulary of regional languages seems to be poor, and does not match the communicative needs required for science and technology.

Furthermore, Webb and Kembo-Sure (2000) reinforce that the ex-colonial language dominance in the educational systems reveals that little attention is devoted to the development of learners' cognitive, affective, and social skills in their first language, or to their skills to use their first languages in technological and intellectual discourse. In conclusion, Manuel & Johnson (2018), assert that parents are not (immune) from the ideology that the dominance of Portuguese is not only restricted to classrooms, businesses, and other public domains, but has also influenced the linguistic ecologies within homes. (p, 127).

The Portuguese language is also viewed as the language of social mobility; those who want to succeed have to speak it well. Children at home grow up with the idea that the Portuguese is the only language to get scientific knowledge and master the school subjects. Finally, thinking that those who cannot perform in Portuguese are uncivilized, uneducated and backward make most Angolan families speaking only Portuguese at home. Consequently, "this creates intergenerational communication problems, as the children do not speak the language of their grandparents.

LANGUAGE AND EXCLUSION

According to Bamgbose (2000) language policy has a huge implication in people's life, when a particular language is stated as official, this means that it has to be used in all government transactions, business, law courts and as the medium of instructions at most level of education. This can results in the division of class of citizens, the class of advantaged-included and the class of disadvantage-the excluded. The advantaged are the community that can use an official language easily and an easy access to education, economy and education. (p,1-2). Additionally, Bamgbose (2000) claims that what is more important is that the advantaged use the same position of advantage to continue to resist change and perpetuate the elitism, which the use of favoured language entails. Their children will have the best education available and they in turn have a better chance of

becoming members of the elite of their own generation. The included are a major stumbling block in the use of African languages in a wider range of domains. Instruction at certain level of education. (op.cit).

EXCLUSION THROUGH AN OFFICIAL LANGUAGE

Bamgbose (2000) argues that exclusion of not speaking the “standard language” can create one of the greatest problems in a country, which in its turn can influence people access to education, public services, jobs, political positions, and effective functioning in the society. Some of the ways of exclusion include the inadequacy to accomplish language requirement, subjection to procedures in an official language, which is completely alien to the excluded person, the inability to participate in situation where the official language is the prescribed medium, and the inability to succeed at school because of not being able to master the medium of instructions. (p,2).

The sole official language is way to exclude people from the full participation in the development of the country. This means that to have access to hospital, court, schools and many other administrative issues, it is essential to speak Portuguese language, it can affect negatively the country’s growth and productivity.

EXCLUSION THROUGH ILLITERACY

According to Bamgbose (2000) the inability of an individual to write and read in the modern world is of a great concern, because lots has to be performed, for example documents, such as letters, documents have to read to him or her by other persons. Forms to be completed can be bank transactions, receipts for purchases, etc. This means that many people are excluded because of illiteracy. Furthermore, the imposition of a literate culture on predominantly oral society is itself a measure of exclusion. “It is the responsibility of the government to redress this unfairness not only pursuing more vigorously adult literacy programmes, but also by paying more attention to oral means of transmission of information. (p,10).

EXCLUSION ARISING FROM LACK OF SHARED MEDIUM IN SCHOOLS

Bamgbose (2000) advocates that the use of a language different from a child’s first language

as a medium of instruction, particularly in early primary education is a matter of language exclusion because it does not value the language the child carries from home, which he or she can speak well. It turns into difficult task for a child to overcome the new content presented in a different language. Moreover Kioko et al, (2008), the child's home language helps an effective understanding and clear explanations. It facilitates children learn concepts and vocabulary, thus bringing them to quick reading and understanding skills. One's own language enables one to express oneself easily, as there is no fear of making mistakes.

The concept or idea of an official language excludes those groups who are not able to speak this language because an official language is associated to the 'standard language. One of the convenient ways of social inclusion reisedes on the fact that one expresses the feelings on his or own language. (p,12).

RESEARCH METHODS

According to Denzin and Lincon (2016) qualitative research is a multi-methodical study, because it incorporates an interpretative, naturalistic and constructivist approach towards its object of study. This means that qualitative research undergoes to the reality in its natural context by giving it a meaning and interpreting the phenomena. (p,40). As Silverman (2013) says a researcher cannot assume that a specific method either qualitative or quantitative is superior than the other, the choice of a method depends on what the researcher is trying to find out, no method of research is better than any other (p. 49). Dorney (2007) and Julião (2018), argues that in qualitative research the selection of participants is open and flexible; participants can be increased after the initial stage during the data collection. (p.126)

PURPOSIVE OR JUDGEMENTAL SAMPLING

According to Dorniey (2007), purposive sampling is a qualitative sampling approach that the researcher uses to select the participants. The participants are selected taking into account some factors and characteristics, for example, individual factors such as education, occupation, as well as social, regiona and ethnic membership. Moreover, in purposive sampling, the researcher can use the following techniques or strategies:

- **Homogeneous sampling:** The researcher selects participants from a particular subgroup who share some important experience relevant to

our study (for example, they have participated in a study-abroad programme).

- **Typical sampling:** The researcher selects participants whose experience is typical with regard to the research focus (for example, they all study a foreign language as a school subject at an intermediate level with moderate success....).
- **Criterion sampling:** The researcher selects participants who meet some specific predetermined criteria (for example, company executives who failed an important language exam). (p, 128).

In this study, homogeneous sampling technique has been used and eleven (11) participants were interviewed. The Participants were selected taken into account some important features that allowed the researcher to obtain substantial information to the study. The participants have studied linguistics or language teaching either at ISCED-BENGUELA or at Higher Polytechnic Institute Jean Piaget- BENGUELA. The participants teach Portuguese language, English and Umbundu. Finally, they were originally from different ethno-linguistic groups (Ovimbundu, Mbundu, Bakongo) etc.

Purposive sampling has been used to select the participants of this study and of its main principles is to select the participants based on certain specific criteria. In this study, the criteria used to select the participants is that they deal with languages, as teachers or teacher trainers and all of them were trained to teach languages, Umbundu, Portugues and English. Moreover, the participants from the Complexo Escolar BGN 2012 Evangélico da Canata- Lobito were included because in this school they teach the Umbundu language as a school subject.

CONTENT ANALYSIS

According to Dorney (2007) in qualitative research, content analysis is used to analyse the meaning of words, phrases, or grammatical structures that turning recordings into textual form and interpreted the deeper meaning of the data. Furthermore, in qualitative content analysis is a flexible method of anlysing and interpreting text data. Its main goal is to provide knowledge and understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. It allows the researcher to analyse and process larger quantities of data and it is flexible in

that the data can be verbal or visual and sampled from other sources as well as collected by the researcher from a natural setting. (p. 245).

Content analysis has been the technique used to analyse data in this research, being a qualitative research, it helped us to interpret the data collected from the tools used during the research.

DATA PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA FROM THE INTERVIEW.

Table (1) below refers to the interview demographic data. It illustrates the number of participants interviewed, age, the first language and other languages that the participants speak.

Note: In the table, school adm, stands for school administrator (adapted from Manuel & Johnson 2018)

Participant	Workplace	Age	First language	Other languages
Teacher 1	Secondary level	37 years	Umbundu	
	Portuguese			
Teacher 2	Secondary level	25 years	Umbundu	
	Portuguese			
Teacher 3	Secondary level	35 years	Portuguese	English
Teacher 4	Secondary level	28 years	Umbundu	
	Portuguese			
Teacher 5	Secondary level	45 years	Kikongo	
	Portuguese, English			
Teacher 6	Private University	36 years	Umbundu	Portuguese
School Adm 1	Secondary level	32 years	Portuguese	Kimbundu
School Adm 2	Secondary level	40 years	Portuguese	Umbundu
Teacher 7	Secondary level	36 years	Portuguese	English
Teacher 8	Secondary level	40 years	Kimbundu	
	Portuguese, English	Teacher 9	Secondary level	30 years
	Umbundu		Portuguese, English	

Table 1. : Interviewees’ demographic data

On the following tables the extracts from the interview will be presented and it will be followed by the analysis of the data. The data that are similar in meaning will be agglutinated.

1. Can Portuguese language and the ‘ national languages’ cohabitate in the school system?

Participants	Participants’ Responses
Teacher 1	“The implementation of the national languages into the school system brings inclusive teaching and learning. We also agree that the system of education in Lobito in particular, Angola in general, is not inclusive because there are still locations here Lobito, for example areas such as <i>Canjala, Culango, Egipto Praia</i> where there are still people who communicate in Umbundu and many people are deprived of studying or give up studying very early because they cannot speak Portuguese”.
Teacher 2	“Most teachers who work in these places cannot speak the language of the residents. And this does not facilitate learning”.
Teacher 3	Yes, “ National languages” can work with the Portuguese because it will bring peace and understanding among people”.
Teacher 4	“The parallel use of the national languages with Portuguese does not only depend on the government which responsible for designing language policy, not only the teachers”.
Teacher 5	“Yes, it is possible, because there are people who do not speak Portuguesese, but they also want to interact with others”.
Teachers 6-7	“The implementation of national languages in schools will help learners to practice them at home and they will be fluent speakers as time goes by”
Teacher 8- 9	“The simple fact of implementing the national languages at school as subjects does not mean that the learners will become fluent, most of the learners’ parents do not even communicate in any of the national languages at home, and the only language used to communicate is Portuguese. There is no way out to be fluent in a language that you do not use.”

<p>School Adm 1-2</p>	<p>“The implementation of our national languages in schools will not make the cohabitation with the Portuguese, because we need to invest more in the national languages, but Portuguese will still be above them”.</p>
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Table 2: The participants’ extracts from the cohabitation between Portuguese and Umbundu in the system of education.

It is important to start the analyse and discussion by saying that if the goal is to integrate a maximum number of learners into the school system of education and eradicate illiteracy, we totally agree that the medium of instruction to be used is of a paramount importance for the success of this desideratum. Furthermore, Angola is a multilingual and multiethnic country, this means that there is an awareness of this particularity from the authorities. One of the main factors of not integrating “ national languages” into the system of education is that the Portuguese language is the medium of instruction is closely associated to the economy, elites and technology. As (Kamwangamulu, 2016) claims national languages have low status compared to ex-colonial languages; national languages are not validated in the market place because, unlike [Portuguese], they are not accorded a status such that knowing them is of material or social benefit to the speaker outside his or immediate speech community.

The parallel use of use of national languages with Portuguese does not only depend on the government, we agree to certain extent, because people in general, institutions, authorities and teachers, etc. can contribute to the promotion of the national languages but their full and effective implementation will depend hugely on the policies and practices from the policymakers. Because it is the duty of the policymakers to determine the domains in which these languages could be used (status planning) and to decide on the written form to be used (corpus planning). It is the government responsibility to accord the “ national languages” a status through the language policies implemented in the country. The way the population view some languages as important for their social mobility or not depends on how the government also treats these languages. In the case of Angola, the “ national languages” have always treated with discrimination comparing to Portuguese language.

We understand that it is possible for there to be a cohabitation between “ national languages” and the Portuguese language in the school system and there has been certain effort on the government for this. However, just insert “ national languages” into the

system of education as a school subject will not bring positive results, because more than inserting it into the system of education, it is essential to create a market for ‘national languages’ through adequate policy so that learners who are being schooled through the medium of instruction of ‘national languages’ must know what that education will do for them in terms of upward social mobility.

It is obvious that there has to be a design of policies and legislation about the use of ‘national languages’, but what is even more important is to turn these legislations into practical actions. For example, Article 19 of the constitutions enriches Portuguese as the only official language in Angola. Although, the constitution upholds the use of African languages, it categorizes them as ‘other languages’. By treating African languages as ‘other languages’, the Constitution creates a situation whereby Portuguese is accorded with high status while African languages are simply treated as other languages, that is what desirable, but not what is the facto promoted (Manuel, 2022, p. 44).

‘National languages’ are viewed for the preservation of our cultural tradition and cultural identity. This reinforces the idea that on the one hand, parents would like their children to learn the national languages; on the other hand, they do not associate it with the professional upward, economy and technology. It is not accidentally that parents prefer Portuguese as a medium of instruction at schools for the education of their children because of the instrumental value of Portuguese medium education rather than the ‘national language’ medium of education.

2. Does globalization impact negatively on the use ‘national languages?’

Participants	Participants’ Responses
Teacher 1	“Globalization has negative influence on the national languages, because there are languages such as Portuguese, English and French which are used for business, education, travel and technology”.
Teacher 2	“ Yes, globalization influences in the negative way the use of national languages, because people will prefer to speak English or French”.
Teacher 3	Yes, “ Globalization makes people not speaking national languages”.
Teacher 4-5	“ Globalization does not help to use national languages because if i want to job i will not need Umbundu or Kimbundu”.

Teachers 6-7	“ Well, it is difficult to talk about this because the government should do more for the use of national languages”
Teacher 8	“ That globalization does not influence negatively the national as the regional languages have not been invested enough to be used globally ”
Teacher 9	My opinion is that globalization influences the use of “ national languages” but the government should do more to preserve it.
School Adm 1-2	“It is necessary to train teachers to teach national languages into the schools so that it can be used like Portuguese or English”.

Table 3: The participants’ extracts whether globalization influence the use of ‘national languages’.

Throughout the discussion it has been stated that “national languages” are hardly used in official institutions, airport, education as a medium of instructions, hospital and administrative work which influences people not to be interested to learn them. Moreover, “national languages” are not equipped with the status to compete with the languages like English, French and Portuguese. For example, English has established itself as a powerful language, it is a tool as well as a resource for social mobility, linguistic superiority, and educational and economic benefits, globalization continues to influence the practices of the national languages in schools, where the ex-colonial languages remain as the sole medium of instruction.

Materials for schools and literary works are mostly published in ex-colonial languages (Kamwangamulu, 2016); Yet, for “national languages” to coexist within globalized world, it is necessary to associated it with economic value in the labor market, because of lack of functional status to ‘national languages’ is one of the main factors that prevents their coexistence with the other languages, like Portuguese, French and English. Ex-colonial languages are viewed as link languages, mainly by the educated elite, as effective means of communication across linguistic and international borders. Therefore, “the preference for a language is in any case not about the inherent nature of the language...[It] happens in all circumstances of language competition in which the speech communities are unevenly matched, whether numerically, militarily, economically or technologically” (Sure and Webb (2000).

Portuguese, English and French are languages that are used globally because through language policy adopted these languages have been empowered to be used as means of communication for varieties of purposes and globally. This is one of the reasons why most important social activities like business, schools, administrative, etc, are performed in Portuguese, English or French.

We also agree that globalization has negative impact to ‘national languages’ to some extent. Because, language is the main tool through which economic transitions, technological equipments, media, etc, are carried out and “national languages” are not accorded with the status to perform these roles. They are marginalized, including by the policymakers, for example, the Angolan constitution of 2010 Article 19, specifies that “the official language of the Republic of Angola is Portuguese...The state shall value and promote the study, teaching, and use of other languages, in addition to the main international languages” (Manuel, 2022)

This means that Portuguese is attributed with high status and “national languages” are just named as other languages on the constitutions. Naming ‘ national languages’ as other languages is also a way of marginalisation. When a language is empowered, it transcends to people who have it as the main tool for social mobility.

3. What can be done to promote the use of ‘ national languages’?

Participants	Participants’ Responses
Teacher 1	“It is necessary to use ‘national languages’ at schools, because learners will be interested to learn them”
Teacher 2	“ To promote ‘ national languages’ we have to use and interact so that people do not forget”.
Teacher 3-4	“. We have to write and publish in national languages”.
Teacher 5	“ People need to speak in ‘national languages’ so that we can promote them ”.
Teachers 6-7	“ One way to promote ‘ national languages’ is to implement them at schools so that children start use them very early”
Teacher 8- 9	“ Children should start learning national languages early. This they will know the importance of national languages”

<p>School Adm 1-2</p>	<p>“ National languages are very important to promote them it is necessary to teach them at schools and also to train teachers that will work in schools. ”.</p>
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Table 4: The participants’ responses on the ways to promote national languages”

Looking at the participants’ extracts, there are many ways that can be adopted to promote ‘national languages’. The government has to be first entity to empower ‘national languages’ through legislation that delimits the contexts that ‘national languages’ have to be used. By delimiting, we mean that there has to be a status for national languages. If this is done effectively writers will start writing and publish in the national languages, which is one way of promoting ‘national languages’. Teaching ‘national languages’ as school subjects at schools is important and will help children to be in contact with ‘national languages’, but this teaching will be successful if the children are aware that the language the language they are learning has an extended use in the community. The teaching model that is used to teach ‘national languages’ is only for statistic reasons. Because, at the end of the day, children will English, French and Portuguese as the most important languages.

Angola is a multilingual country with a salient discursive heterogeneity, and this implies complex relations between language discourse, power and identity. That is to say, language and discourse are not autonomous entities because they are produced politically and discursively, inscribed into the regimes of linguistic signification and power (Manuel, 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

This study has helped to understand that Portuguese is undoubtedly the dominant language and the language that unifies the nation, unfortunately. The findings also show that linguistic heterogeneity and diversity brings about discursive and cultural tensions that lead to social hierarchization, marginalization and exclusion. The stigma and marginalization associated to ‘national languages’ and their speakers derives from the prestige and the market value of Portuguese. Within the market place, the language has a huge value and importance because it is the means by which speakers establish who has the right to speak, what knowledge is credited, and most frequently applied.

From the linguistic market perspective, language has a market value as it is used strategically to maintain, control and establish power relations. Therefore, the findings conclude that national languages and their “speakers lack the linguistic capital necessary to access the cultural, economic, and political resources necessary for their individual development”.

Additionally, we have to conclude that Portuguese is the language used as the prerequisite for access in science, technology and education. English, Portuguese and French are used as prerequisites for the access to science and technology and there is an ideology that without these languages, it is difficult to be successful at school and business, etc. This kind of linguistic dependency and the lack of a clear policy to overcome it has brought forth enormous barriers to the development of the country. The study has also concluded that there is no clear policy to promote “national languages”. The kind of teaching that is done at schools is not efficient because the curriculum does not specify what the learners will be doing with the Umbundu’s language in the professional life.

Any language in the world can be used for whatever purposes, however in a multilingual country, it is important to design a language policy that empowers all the language to avoid exclusions not just of a language, but towards people who cannot communicate in the language official language. Negative attitudes to language is the synonymous with social exclusion, as a consequence many people cannot have full participation to the development of their community of language reasons. Teaching and learning would be more successful if one was taught through the medium of instructions that he or she can communicate.

The study recommends the government design clear language policy that can promote all language in a Multilingual settings and one of these policies is the regional officialization of “national language”. For example, the officialization of Umbundu’s language on the south and central of Angola. This would oblige people to learn the Umbundu language to get access to social services, like hospitals, schools, administratives, etc.

Finally, finding specific books on “national languages” has been the main limitations we have faced during the research and for further research we recommend market values for “national languages”.

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